

School Name:

Farzanegan High School (NODET - SAMPAD)

Research Title:

**Investigating the Status of Pasteurized Milk Products in Terms of Freezing
Point Factor Using a **Cryoscope****

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Research Abstract:

Today, the increase in the price of goods, especially edible milk, is one of the economic problems of society. Also, milk is an important food and a very important drink. Given the high nutritional value and the increase in the price of edible milk, the purity of pasteurized milk and its quality are important issues that many people are looking for. This is a very important and significant issue because it is directly related to the health of citizens in society. Milk is also the main food for infants and the food required by the human body, especially in children.

Pure water freezes at 0 degrees Celsius. And as any substance dissolves in it, the freezing point decreases, and similarly, milk nutrients, including lactose,¹ salts, including chloride ions,² etc., decrease the freezing point (Source 4)

In the experiments, an attempt has been made to obtain the freezing point of milk samples using a cryoscope device and determine the quality and quantity of each of them according to the Iranian National Standard No. 93

In this research, we can consider the availability of samples and the lack of use of chemicals in milk and informing people about the quality and standards observed in pasteurized milk as positive and useful points of the project.

Research topic: Investigating the status of pasteurized milk products in terms of freezing point factor using a cryoscope device

Keywords: pasteurized milk, freezing point, cryoscope device, milk quality and purity

1- Lactose: sugar present in milk

2- A type of ion present in water

Introduction:

Humans have always sought health and well-being, and in this regard, they have tried to make sufficient use of the available facilities and materials. Given the high nutritional value of milk and the increase in its price in recent months, the quality and standard of pasteurized milk has attracted the attention of people. Also, the absence of milk in the diet causes vitamin deficiency in the body.

I had heard in the media that the price of pasteurized milk had increased, and since milk is of great importance and is used to prepare other dairy products, it occurred to me that perhaps their quality had not changed due to the increase in milk prices and was in accordance with the Iranian National Standard No. 93, which deals with the properties of pasteurized milk.

(Source 8)

Pure water freezes at 0 degrees Celsius, and as any substance dissolves in it, the freezing point decreases. Similarly, milk nutrients, including lactose, salts, including chloride ions, etc., decrease the freezing point. The most important factors affecting the freezing point of milk are water added during the milking and collection stages, aging and high microbial load, mastitis, and adulteration, including the addition of ionizable substances such as salt, etc.

(Source 4)

The freezing point of milk is one of the most stable physical properties of milk.

The freezing point shift is directly proportional to the number of particles in solution.

Measuring the freezing point of milk is used to control the adulteration of water added to milk.

The freezing point of milk is determined primarily by the major components that have low molecular weight, namely lactose and salts.

The freezing point and boiling point of milk are slightly lower and higher than water, respectively. Milk freezes at a temperature between -0.543 and -0.546 (Source 9)

Their freezing points in the Iranian National Standard are from -0.507 to -0.545. (Source 8)

In this research, I want to determine their standardization and find out their purity and quality by obtaining the freezing points of pasteurized milk and comparing them with each other, using a cryoscope. My main task is to examine the freezing point of pasteurized milk samples and compare them with the Iranian National Standard No. 93. The quality of milk is determined as follows: Obtaining the freezing points of the samples using a cryoscope and selecting a milk sample whose number is further from zero (the freezing point of water). To know the standard and identify the highest quality pasteurized milk, I used six samples of pasteurized milk (Pak, Pegah, Kale, Manizan, Ramek, Damdaran)

A cryoscope or a device for measuring the freezing point of milk, or a device for measuring the amount of water added to milk through the freezing point, can measure the amount of water added to milk. A cryoscope or cryostar measures the water added to milk by measuring the freezing point of milk. (Source 9)

Research Background:

1-The need to revise the freezing point index of pasteurized milk in the 93rd National Standard to improve the safety of dairy products - Sahargahi Badrieh, Ramadani Pedram, Ghambarzadeh Hadith

Kermanshah University of Medical Sciences (Source 4)

The emphasis of the competent authorities on the freezing point of milk without simultaneously considering other factors such as the percentage of minerals and electronic conductivity leads to an increase in the possibility of milk adulteration with easily ionizable substances such as salt. (Source 5)

2- The effect of storage time and acidity of raw milk on the freezing point

Fateme Pourfallah - Department of Biochemistry, Pasteur Institute of Iran, Tehran, Iran

3- Types of milk adulteration and their identification methods

Food Industry Engineering Student Scientific Association, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad (Source 6)

Research Method:

This research uses an experimental method that has independent, dependent, and control variables. In this research, we reach the real goal through experimentation.

Project Question: Does the purity of pasteurized milk (Pak, Ramek, Pegah, Manizan, Damdaran, Kaleh) in terms of freezing point meet the national standard?

Research Objectives:

General Objectives: To examine the freezing point of milk from reputable factories (Pak, Ramek, Pegah, Manizan, Damdaran, Kale) using a cryoscope in the laboratory of the Kermanshah Standards Office and to help people prepare pasteurized milk with higher purity and better quality.

Sub-Objectives: To examine the freezing point of reputable pasteurized milk samples and their compliance with the Iranian National Standard No. 93. Also, to obtain the purity level of each of them and to examine the quality of the samples.

Hypothesis: I think that the milks (Pak, Ramek, Pegah, Manizan, Damdaran, Kale) available in the market comply with the National Standard No. 93

Independent Variable: Freezing Point

Dependent Variable: Milk

Controlled Variable: Milk Fat, Moisture

Data collection:

Given that our research method is experimental and requires seeing all stages of the experiment from beginning to end, we chose the observation method because:

- 1- We establish direct auditory and visual contact with the environment, which gives us accurate and real information
- 2- It provides us with a wider volume of information and cultural problems have less impact on the experiment

Materials and methods:

1- Pak, Ramek, Pegah, Manizan, Damdaran, Kale milk samples

2- Pipette

3- Cryoscope device

4- Test tubes

On 18/4/1401, I went to the neighborhood stores to buy pasteurized milk samples. I prepared 6 samples of pasteurized milk Pak, Ramek, Pegah, Manizan, Damdaran, Kale 3% fat from different factories. Then I kept them in cool conditions and went to the Kermanshah Standard Department laboratory. Using a pipette, I poured the required amount (about 4 cc) of milk from each sample into small test tubes. I placed each of the milk samples in the test tube in turn in the cryoscope device. I noted the numbers and percentage of water that the cryoscope device showed for each sample.

Then, in the next step, I compared the numbers obtained from the tests and determined their quality and purity and put the results in a table.

In the tests and freezing point obtained from each sample, we observe that in the milk samples, the water content in all of them is 0% and their freezing point is standard (from -0.507 to -0.545). Also, Ramak milk has higher purity and higher quality than other milk samples.

Table of freezing points of milk and their water percentage

Water percentage	Freezing point	Milk sample
%0	-0.5120	Pak milk
%0	-0,5187	Manizan milk
%0	-0.5112	Pegah milk
%0	-0.5140	Kale milk
%0	-0.5281	Ramak milk
%0	-0.5120	Damdaran milk

Explanation: As you can see in the table above, the freezing point of Ramak milk (sample 5) is further from 0 (freezing point of water) than other samples and has higher purity and quality. Pegah milk has a lower purity and its freezing point is closer to 0. And it has a relatively lower quality compared to other samples. However, the freezing point of all samples is within the standard range and the water content in them is 0%

Freezing point chart of milk and its quality and purity

Explanation: According to the numbers obtained from the cryoscope device, Ramak milk has a higher purity than other samples and its freezing point is further from 0. Ramak milk has a higher quality than other milk samples. After that, the following are the milks of Manizan, Kaleh, Damdaran, Pak, and Pegah, in that order.

Data analysis:

According to the tests and data review, the cryoscope device showed the freezing point of Ramek milk as -0.5281 , which is further from 0 (freezing point of water) than other samples. It has high quality. Pegah milk, with a freezing point of -0.5112 , is closer to 0 than other samples and has lower purity and quality.

Their quality is, in order, after Ramek milk, Manizan milk with a freezing point of -0.5187 , Kaleh milk with a freezing point of -0.5140 , Damdaran and Pak milk with a freezing point of -0.5120 , and finally Pegah milk with a freezing point of -0.5112

But in all milk samples, their freezing point and purity are in a standard and appropriate state.

Conclusion and summary:

The numbers obtained from the cryoscope device and their comparison showed that all pasteurized milk samples (Pak, Ramek, Pegah, Manizan, Damdaran, Kaleh) have complied with the national standards of Iran and all their freezing points are in accordance with the range of national standard No. 93

In the comparison of the tests, it was determined that Ramek milk with a lower freezing point has the highest quality and Pegah milk with a higher freezing point has the lowest quality compared to the other samples. Therefore, the answer to the project question was confirmed and the hypothesis of this research was proven.

By testing this idea, we have helped all the people of the world who should enjoy the blessing of health and we inform them that these pasteurized milks available in the market are all standard and do not cause any harm to human health.

Suggestions:

- 1- Buy milk from reputable factories instead of local milk (especially in the hot seasons) because there is strict control in terms of microbial load, aflatoxin, which is produced by a type of fungus, malt fever, and other issues.
- 2- The purity of milk is lower in the hot seasons because livestock is subjected to heat stress, and especially in tropical regions, its quality decreases compared to cold regions. It is better to provide an environment like the cold seasons in large and advanced sheds.
- 3- As you have heard, fodder plays a vital role for livestock, and if the fodder is moldy, it reduces the volume of milk, which will not be in the interest of the farmer, the factory, and the consumer. It is better to use nanoscience to prolong the shelf life of fodder so that it does not become moldy later.
- 4- As you know, large dairy cows produce more milk annually but it is more watery, while smaller breeds produce less but it is more concentrated and of better quality. This problem can be solved to some extent by using genetics and breeding.

Sources:

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